

IMPORTANCE OF THE MEDICINAL GINKO BILOBA PLANT

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Abstract

Ginko leaves are recognized and valued in many countries of the world for their unique healing properties. They are used in the production of expensive medicines as well as in traditional medicine. At home, doctors prepare alcohol and water infusions. Herbal teas, which cost people much less than various imports of medicines

Key words: *ginko extract, Peripheral circulation, bacteria, virusa.*

Аннотация.

Доривор ўсимликлар орасида гинкого барглари биринчи ўринда туради, улар биринчи марта 5000 йил олдин Хитой табиблари томонидан тилга олинган. Гинкго барглари ноёблиги учун дунёнинг кўплаб мамлакатларида тан олинади ва қадрланади. Улар қимматбаҳо дори-дармонларни ишлаб чиқаришда, шунингдек халқ таъбибатида қўлланилади. Уйда табиблар спиртли ичимликлар ва сув инфузионлари, ўсимлик чойи тайёрлайдилар, бу одамлар учун турли хил импорт қилинган дори-дармонларга қараганда анча арзонроқ

Kalit so'z: *Гинко билоба, ҳашорот, бактерия, вирус, периферик қон айланиши, интродукция.*

Аннотация.

Листья гинкго признаны и ценятся во многих странах мира за свои уникальные целебные свойства. Их используют при производстве дорогих лекарств также в народной медицине. В домашних условиях врачи готовят спиртовые и водные настои, травяные чаи, которые обходятся людям гораздо дешевле, чем различные импортные лекарства.

Ключевые слова:*Экстракт гинкго, периферическое кровообращение, бактерии ,вирусы.*

Ginkgo biloba is the oldest of all ancient plants on the planet. The last extant species of this family, Ginkgophytes, are considered extinct. For more than 300 million years, Ginkgo biloba has been struggling to survive, and now the plant is in danger of extinction.

The homeland of the tree is China. Because it is very difficult to transport the seedlings of this tree, it is not widely distributed on earth. Ginkgo biloba is a tree called "Living Fossil" by famous biologist Charles Darwin.

In Asia, the medicinal properties of ginkgo have been used for 5000 years. The active substances of ginkgo are found in the leaves. Ginkgo biloba tree also grew in Europe, but it disappeared during the ice age. In 1712, German doctor and botanist Engel Bert Kaempfer brought Ginkgo from Japan to Europe. [1]

The healing properties of ginkgo include:

- It improves blood circulation in veins, arteries, capillaries, as a result of which the supply of oxygen to all organs and tissues of living organisms improves, restores brain memory;
- Does not allow blood clots to form in blood vessels by sticking platelets;
- Helps to eliminate asthma attacks;
- An indispensable tool in the treatment of diabetes;
- An effective tool in the treatment of sexual weakness, insomnia and depression;

- It has the ability to prevent the growth of metastases in oncological diseases;

Ginkgo biloba plant is a 2-housed plant. Ovaries develop on female trees, and pollen on male trees. It grows naturally only in China, but nevertheless it is cultivated in a number of countries with a temperate climate. It can be found in North America, East Asia and some European countries, where it is cultivated for the needs of the pharmaceutical market. Nowadays, we can find this unique plant in many botanical gardens, including in Russia. [2] Ginkgo can grow up to 40 min height, the average life span is very long, it can live more than 1000 years. Ginkgo is also very resistant to insect, bacterial and viral infections and air pollution.

Ginkgo is used in the production of many types of drugs in the pharmaceutical industry due to the fact that it acts as a strong antioxidant and prevents cell damage. Because of this feature the first plant that came back to life after the atomic bomb explosion in Hiroshima was the Ginkgo's bud.[4]

In 1965, the first Ginkgo leaf extract was produced and registered in Germany, which marked the beginning of modern Ginkgo therapy. Since then, the extract has been used as an effective agent in the treatment of cerebral circulatory disorders and peripheral circulatory disorders. To date, Ginkgo extract is the most studied and marketed medicinal plant in the world.[3] In decorative gardening, it is valued for the beauty of the crown and open leaves. Often used in landscape design.

The ginkgo plant can withstand a short cooling of 3000 C. It grows well in wet soil, but constant water flow in the place ,where it is grown, has a negative effect. In the cold climate of Central Russia, it is necessary to wrap the tree in winter. It grows in the form of a bush and grows very slowly. A plant highly resistant to air pollution. In countries with a mild climate, it grows up to 15 m and

bears fruit every year. It is propagated by seeds or vegetatively.

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